

SOME ASPECTS OF TEACHING MICROBIOLOGY

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Abstract. The article discusses some aspects of teaching microbiology at a medical university, focusing on the implementation of a systematic approach in the education system, the essence of which is to consider the object of research and practical activity in the unity of external and internal connections in space and time.

Keywords: medical school, teaching microbiology, activation of educational and cognitive activities of students, systems approach.

INTRODUCTION

Improving the quality of higher education is one of the pressing problems in connection with the requirements imposed both on the teaching process itself and on its direct objects - the teacher and the student. In particular, these requirements are determined by the dynamic situation on the labor market, the intensive development of Uzbek society, and the informatization of the scientific and educational space. That is why education should form new qualities, first of all, the professional competitiveness of future specialists in modern conditions, which presupposes not only the comprehension of theoretical knowledge, but also the ability to apply acquired knowledge in practice, a high level of general intellectual development, initiative, mobility, creativity etc. [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Changes in recent years in the field of higher education have highlighted the contrasts between established traditions and innovations in the organization of the educational process and have necessitated the introduction of the latest (innovative) education systems for the development of the pedagogical process as a whole [2, 4]. Such an innovative educational system, which has become widespread among higher educational institutions, has become a credit-modular education system, the main goals of which are to create conditions for the development of the personality of a future specialist, the formation of his creative and self-educational activities [2, 3, 5].

The purpose of the article is to reveal the features of teaching the academic discipline "Microbiology, Virology and Immunology" for students of medical universities in Uzbekistan in terms of modern requirements of the scientific space.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The lecture course defines the theoretical basis of the content of the discipline “Microbiology, Virology and Immunology”, introduces students to the fundamental principles and general principles of teaching microbiology at a university. In terms of improving the educational process, the use of modern computer technologies, in particular multimedia lectures and presentations, can significantly increase the information content, illustrativeness and, accordingly, the quality of students’ perception of educational material. In addition, a multimedia lecture allows the teacher to significantly save time, allowing a more detailed explanation of new material. The use of such presentations at lectures activates cognitive processes, on which the student’s self-development, and increasing the significance and visibility of microbiology as a science, and the quality of teaching the subject, and the implementation of program educational material, largely depend. Also, a multimedia lecture increases the level of emotional and professional interest, which is one of the most important tasks in improving the educational process [3].

The purpose of practical classes is to acquire theoretical knowledge on the subject and master the methods of microbiological, virological and serological diagnostics, etiotropic therapy and specific prevention of infectious diseases. In the process of this work, students study the biological properties of pathogenic and non-pathogenic microorganisms, viruses and the patterns of their interaction with the macroorganism, the human population and the external environment, determine methods of microbiological and virological diagnostics, etiotropic therapy and specific prevention of infectious diseases. diseases, understand the basic mechanisms of formation of the immune response of the human body, master practical skills in staining smears and techniques for preparing immunobiological preparations used for diagnosis, treatment and specific prevention of infectious diseases.

In the process of teaching microbiology, virology and immunology, the specifics of studying the subject for students of the medical and pharmaceutical faculties are also taken into account. It should be noted that the formation of the worldview of a future specialist, the development of his personality is influenced not only by training and the program content of education, but also by intellectual and creative activity and self-education. These phenomena in the medical education system are inextricably linked, which is due to changes in the requirements for the current state of professional training and specialization, as well as the extremely rapid loss of relevance of information. The knowledge

acquired in higher medical institutions is no longer enough; the leading focus is on continuous education, which extends throughout the life of a specialist [5]. Therefore, one of the main tasks of training future specialists in medical universities is to learn to acquire knowledge and skills, as well as experience in cognitive and creative independent activity. At the same time, there is a process of formation of psychological, theoretical and practical readiness for intellectual, creative activity, as well as for the process of self-education.

CONCLUSION

To summarize, we note that in order to enhance the educational and cognitive activity of students and the formation of future medical specialists, the entire process of teaching microbiology, virology and immunology is built on the principle of a systematic approach, taking into account the individual characteristics of the participants in the educational process.

References:

1. Moroz O.G., Padalka O.S., Yurchenko V.I. Pedagogy and psychology of high school. – Moscow, 2013. – 267 p.
2. Gafurov, B. Z. (2022). Analysis of medical version in texts of advertising of hygiene products in the fight against COVID-19 (on the material of Russian and Uzbek languages). Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL).
3. Gafurov, B. Z. (2021). Study of advertising texts in Russian on the topic of medical terminology. International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT).–Indonesia, 26(1), 586-590.
4. Гафуров, Б. З. (2021). АНАЛИЗ ЛИНГВОСТАТИСТИЧЕСКОЙ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ АКЦЕНТНЫХ ФОНОВАРИАНТОВ ИМЕН СУЩЕСТВИТЕЛЬНЫХ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 4(1-1).
5. Gafurov, B. Z. (2021). Medical terminology in advertising text. Scientific reports of Bukhara State University, 5(3), 30-40.
6. Gafurov, B. Z. Similarities and differences of segment background options for Russian, Uzbek and English languages. Monografia pokonferency jnascience, Research, development, 26, 17-19.
7. Гафуров, Б. З. Тексты С Фоностилистическими Фоновариантами И Их Перевод (На Материале Узбекского Языка). Ilim Нам Jamiyet, 72.
8. Zakirovich, G. B. (2023). THE MAIN FEATURES OF KINESTHETIC STYLE IN LEARNING PROCESS. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(5), 61-69.

9. Gafurov, B. Z. (2023). ADVERTISEMENT TEXT AS A WAY OF INFLUENCE ON THE AUDIENCE. Academia Science Repository, 4(5), 443-448.
10. Gafurov, B. Z. (2023). REFLECTION OF STYLISTICALLY MARKED VOCABULARY IN ADVERTISEMENT TEXTS. Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence, 2(5), 425-428.
11. Аникеев В.В., Лукомская К.А. Руководства к практическим занятиям по микробиологии. – М. 2017.
12. Zakirovich, G. B. (2023). ACCURACY AND FLUENCY IN LANGUAGE TEACHING. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(05), 19-25.
13. Zakirovich, G. B. (2023). SPECIFICATION OF ERROR CORRECTION IN LANGUAGE LEARNING PROSESS. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(05), 8-13.
14. Gafurov, B. (2023). THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CULTURE AND LANGUAGE IN LEARNING PROCESS. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 3(5), 55-63.
15. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). Service Parts of Speech as an Important Component of Advertising Text in Russian and Uzbek Languages (By the Material of Advertising in the Sphere of Medicine). European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science, 3, 1-7.
16. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). Discourse about the peculiarities of the theme of male gender in advertising texts in Russian and Uzbek (on the material of medical vocabulary). EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 2(2), 4-8.
17. Zakirovich, G. B. (2023). Structural-Semantic Features of Conversion Models "Adjective-Noun". American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(9), 306-310.
18. Gafurov, B. Z. (2022). Neologisms and their functions in the field of medicine. Journal of intellectual property and human rights, 1(08), 41-44.
19. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). The Theme of Female Gender in the Texts of Advertising in Russian and Uzbek Languages (On the Material of Medical Vocabulary). Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT, 2(1), 23-29.
20. Problems of illumination [Text]: scientific method. zb.: Vip.44/ Ministry of education and science, scientific method. center of vis. illuminate; editorial board: V.G. Flint (head ed.) [ta n.] 2018. 132 p.

21. Gurzhiy A. Methodological approaches to assessing and predicting the development of high lighting / A. Gurzhiy, V. Gapon // Lighting of Ukraine. – 2016. – No. 1. – P. 23–31.
22. Slepkan Z.I. Scientific ambushes of the pedagogical process in high school: Head. pos_b. –Vishcha School, 2015. – 239 p.
23. Zinchuk V.V. Innovative teaching methods in the system of teaching classical disciplines // Modern educational technologies and methodological support in higher medical school: Materials of the Republican conference with international participation. – Grodno, 2010. – pp. 104–107.

